

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENFORCEMENT OF THE EMERGENCY ARBITRATOR'S DECISION

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ABSTRACT

Emergency Arbitrator refers to an arbitrator appointed by an arbitration institution directly by the parties to an arbitration agreement in the process of international civil and commercial dispute resolution, due to the urgency of the situation before the establishment of the formal arbitral tribunal. The decision of the emergency arbitrator in an emergency arbitrator procedure is an interim measure, and the enforcement of the interim measure is the key to the emergency arbitrator procedure. There is no unified view on the nature of the decision of an emergency arbitrator. Hong Kong, Singapore and New Zealand have directly provided for the enforceability of emergency arbitrations in their arbitration laws. There is still a lack of agreement in other countries or regions of the world on the enforceability of an emergency arbitrator's decision. The enforcement of decisions made by emergency arbitrators is still a controversial issue.

1. Definition of Emergency Arbitrator

Emergency Arbitrator refers to an arbitrator appointed by an arbitration institution directly by the parties to an arbitration agreement in the process of international civil and commercial dispute resolution, due to the urgency of the situation before the establishment of the formal arbitral tribunal. As a special remedy before the formation of the arbitral tribunal, the emergency arbitrator procedure, to a certain extent, reflects the extension of the limited power of the arbitral tribunal, which can provide interim relief to the parties to the arbitration before the constitution of the arbitral

tribunal, broaden the channels for the parties to apply for interim relief, avoid the risk of loss of evidence, transfer or damage to the property involved in the case, and at the same time, the rights of the parties to the arbitration can be fully covered within the framework of arbitration. It can better protect the interests of the parties, guarantee the smooth operation of the arbitration procedure and the smooth execution of the arbitration award[1]. In accordance with the prevailing practice of the emergency arbitrator rules of international arbitration institutions, the arbitral institution will appoint an emergency arbitrator at the same time as

or after the application of the parties, and the emergency arbitrator will decide on emergency interim relief for the parties. The decision on emergency interim relief is binding on the parties. If the law of the place of arbitration or enforcement gives enforcement effect to the emergency arbitrator's decision, then a party may further apply to a court for enforcement. Generally, the jurisdiction of the emergency arbitrator and the decision made by the emergency arbitrator are effective until the formation of the arbitral tribunal, after which the emergency arbitrator no longer has jurisdiction over the case and the arbitral tribunal has the right to modify and terminate the decision made by the emergency arbitrator.

2. The Development of Emergency Arbitrator

With the new changes in the international economy, the emergence of new business models and transactions, and the internationalization and diversification of commercial disputes, international arbitration institutions are objectively required to innovate their rules in line with the development of economic patterns, and an important aspect of the innovation of arbitration rules is the establishment of a special procedural framework to enhance the efficiency function. Since in international civil and commercial disputes, the parties to the arbitration and the arbitrators may come from different countries or regions, the property involved in the case may be transferred or concealed before the formation of the arbitral tribunal, the key evidence related to the case may be destroyed, and many factors cause a long dispute resolution period, resulting in the arbitration process not being able to function as it should.

Therefore, in order to mitigate the risks caused by such negative factor, to reduce the reliance of arbitral tribunals on courts, and to meet the urgent interim relief needs of the parties, the emergency arbitrator procedure was created. Emergency arbitrator procedure has worked well in the practice of international commercial arbitration, and the number of emergent interim relief requests filed by parties under the Emergency Arbitrator Procedure has increased each year.

Article 17. Power of arbitral tribunal to order interim measures of the « UNCITRAL Model Law On International Commercial Arbitration 1985» clearly stipulates that: "Unless otherwise agreed by the parties, the arbitral tribunal may, at the request of a party, order any party to take such interim measure of protection as the arbitral tribunal may consider necessary in respect of the subjectmatter of the dispute. The arbitral tribunal may require any party to provide appropriate security in connection with such measure[2]."

In 1990, the International Chamber of Commerce proposed a "Pre-Arbitral Referee Procedure" and published the «PRE-ARBITRAL REFEREE RULES», which stipulate that: "These Rules concern a procedure called the "Pre-Arbitral Referee Procedure", which provides for the immediate appointment of a person (the "Referee") who has the power to make certain Orders prior to the arbitral tribunal or national court competent to deal with the case (the "Competent Authority") being seized of it[3]."

The Emergency Arbitrator procedure was finally established in the «American Arbitration Association-International Arbitration Rules»[4] of 2009, and then major arbitration institutions in the world

introduced the Emergency Arbitrator procedure one after another. The Singapore introduced the emergency arbitrator procedure in 2010, and it is also the first international arbitration institution in Asia to introduce an emergency arbitrator procedure in the arbitration rules. According to «SIAC 2020 Annual Report»: "SIAC received 20 applications to appoint an Emergency Arbitrator (EA) and accepted all 20 requests in 2020, bringing the total number of EA applications accepted by SIAC since the introduction of these provisions to 114 in 2010[5]."

The Hong Kong introduced the emergency arbitrator procedure in 2012. According to «HKIAC 2021 Statistics»: "Four emergency arbitrator applications were submitted to HKIAC in 2021. The total number of emergency arbitrator applications filed with HKIAC up to 2021 is 31[6]."

3. Features of the Emergency Arbitrator Procedure

After more than decades of change, the emergency arbitrator procedure has become increasingly popular with parties to arbitration and has been adopted by major international arbitration institutions. The reason for this is that, compared to traditional emergency remedies such as court preservation, the emergency arbitrator procedure has the following unique advantages:

Stronger autonomy of will: parties can apply for the emergency arbitrator procedure according to their own needs before the formal arbitral tribunal is constituted, which is initiated by the parties to the arbitration and respects the will of the parties to the arbitration to the greatest extent possible. Parties using the emergency arbitrator procedure can basically avoid judicial interference except

for the enforcement stage, which more emphasizes the autonomy of the parties.

Stronger confidentiality: In legal practice, a large proportion of parties choose arbitration because it is more confidential than litigation in the courts. The reason for this is that, as two different dispute resolution methods, court proceedings are based on the principle of public hearings and therefore less confidential, while arbitration institutions generally hear cases in private. Commercial cases mostly involve commercial secrets, the application of the emergency arbitrator procedures allows the entire process of a dispute case to be included in the arbitration process, which can better meet the parties' needs for confidentiality and can effectively protect the confidentiality of important information on which commercial entities rely.

More efficient features: Most arbitration institutions will clearly stipulate the time limit for emergency arbitrator procedures in their arbitration rules, and truly play the "emergency" role of emergency interim preservation, so that the legitimate rights and interests of the parties can be protected in the shortest possible time. According to the provisions of the arbitration rules of major international arbitration institutions, the time period from the application, initiation to the final decision of emergency preservation measures has greatly shortened the time it may take for judicial preservation to take the same measures, and the time schedule is also more convenient to be compact. For example, "HKIAC 2018 Arbitration Rules" and "SIAC 2016 Arbitration Rules" stipulate that the Arbitration Center must seek to appoint an emergency arbitrator within 24 hours after receipt of both the

Application. In addition, the emergency arbitrator shall make a decision, order or award on the Application within 14 days from the date on which Arbitration Center transmitted the case file to the emergency arbitrator. The 24-hour appointment period and the 14-day decision period fully reflect the efficiency of the emergency arbitrator procedures.

Consideration of impartiality: The emergency arbitrator appointed by the arbitration institution according to the application of the parties shall remain neutral in the process of exercising power, be independent of the disputing parties in the arbitration case, and shall not favor any party. At the same time, the emergency arbitrator is generally not allowed to participate in the follow-up arbitration hearings without the unanimous consent of both parties. The emergency arbitral tribunal will be dissolved on the date of the establishment of the formal arbitral tribunal, and all the case files will be handed over to the arbitral tribunal. Therefore, it can prevent the occurrence of unfair results due to the misjudgment or bias of the emergency arbitrator in the case, and ensure the fairness of the entire arbitration procedure to the greatest extent.

4. Emergency Arbitrator Procedure in Hong Kong and Singapore

Articles 23.1 and 23.3 of the «2018 HKIAC Administered Arbitration Rules»[7] and Articles 30.1 and 30.2 of the «Singapore International Arbitration Centre Arbitration Rules 6th Edition, 1 August 2016»[8] stipulate that the parties have the right to apply to the arbitration tribunal for emergency relief.

Both of them specify emergency relief in detail in the appendix, but the application

for emergency arbitrator procedures, the acceptance of applications and the appointment of emergency arbitrators, the disclosure and withdrawal of emergency arbitrators, emergency arbitrator procedures, and decisions of emergency arbitrators. There are big differences in the specific content of emergency arbitrators' procedural expenses.

4.1. Emergency Arbitrator Procedure in Hong Kong

The Hong Kong International Center introduced an emergency arbitrator Procedure in the «2013 Administered Arbitration Rules». According to the arbitration rules, a party requiring Emergency Relief may, concurrent with or following the filing of a Notice of Arbitration but prior to the constitution of the arbitral tribunal, submit an application (the "Application") for the appointment of an emergency arbitrator (the "Emergency Arbitrator") to HKIAC. The Hong Kong International Arbitration Centre launched a rules revision process in August 2017 to consider amendments to the 2013 HKIAC Administered Arbitration Rule (2013 rules), having regard to the latest trends in international arbitration, feedback from users and HKIAC's past case management experience.

The 2013 rules have been widely regarded as one of the market-leading arbitration procedures with several innovative provisions, such as the availability of two options to pay arbitrators' fees, leading the HKIAC to receive a nomination for a GAR award in 2014. Notwithstanding this, after multiple rounds of public consultation, the HKIAC considers that it is time to update the 2013 rules with certain amendments possibly to benefit users.

The HKIAC has announced several new provisions to add to the 2018 Administered Arbitration Rules (2018 rules), intended to improve the procedural certainty and cost-efficiency of HKIAC arbitration. The provisions primarily address the following: The HKIAC's Emergency Arbitrator Procedure was updated to confirm the timing of filing an application for emergency relief, the test for issuing such relief and the maximum fees payable to an emergency arbitrator. The procedure was expanded to allow a party to file an application before, concurrent with or after the submission of a Notice of Arbitration, but prior to the constitution of an arbitral tribunal. All time limits under the procedure was shortened and an emergency arbitrator's fees will be subject to a maximum amount. A new provision was added to clarify, among other things, that the granting of emergency arbitrator relief will be subject to the same test applied by an arbitral tribunal when deciding whether to issue an interim measure.

4.2. Emergency Arbitrator Procedure in Singapore

The Singapore International Arbitration Centre introduced emergency arbitration procedures in the Arbitration Rules Of The Singapore International Arbitration Centre (4Th Edition, 1 July 2010) , "a party in need of emergency relief may, concurrent with or following the filing of a Notice of Arbitration but prior to the constitution of the Tribunal, make an application for emergency interim relief. The party shall notify the Registrar and all other parties in writing of the nature of the relief sought and the reasons why such relief is required on an emergency basis. The application shall also set forth the reasons why the

party is entitled to such relief. Such notice may be given by e-mail, facsimile transmission or other reliable means, but must include a statement certifying that all other parties have been notified or an explanation of the steps taken in good faith to notify other parties. The application shall also be accompanied by payment of any fees set by the Registrar for proceedings pursuant to this Schedule 1[9]." In order to further speed up the process of emergency arbitration, under the 2016 Rules, the timetable for appointing emergency arbitrators is within one (1) day from the date of receipt of the party's application for emergency relief and the payment of the fee in the master book, not Within the original one (1) business day. The 2016 Rules also stipulate that the order and award of interim relief measures should be made within at most 14 days from the appointment of the emergency arbitrator. In order to ensure that the emergency arbitration procedure is more cost-effective than any other case, unless the master book decides otherwise, the emergency arbitrator's fee is fixed at SGD 25,000[10].

5. Enforcement of the emergency arbitrator's decision

5.1.The problem of enforcement of the emergency arbitrator's decision

The decision of the emergency arbitrator in an emergency arbitrator procedure is an interim measure, and the enforcement of the interim measure is the key to the emergency arbitrator procedure. The enforcement of decisions made by emergency arbitrators has been a controversial issue.

«Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York, 1958)» stipulate that:"This

Convention shall apply to the recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards made in the territory of a State other than the State where the recognition and enforcement of such awards are sought, and arising out of differences between persons, whether physical or legal. It shall also apply to arbitral awards not considered as domestic awards in the State where their recognition and enforcement are sought[11].” From this we can conclude that the New York Convention applies to foreign arbitral awards, but it is inconclusive whether it applies to interim measures. It is argued that a distinction should first be made between whether the decision of the emergency arbitrator is an "order" or an "award". If the decision of the emergency arbitrator is an award, then the award can be recognized and enforced worldwide under the New York Convention. If it is merely an order, then enforceability is difficult to determine. However, there is no unified view on the nature of the decision of an emergency arbitrator. Hong Kong, Singapore and New Zealand have directly provided for the enforceability of emergency arbitrations in their arbitration laws. There is still a lack of agreement in other countries or regions of the world on the enforceability of an emergency arbitrator's decision.

5.2. National and regional legislative provisions on of the emergency arbitrator's decision

(1) UNCITRAL Model Law

«UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration 1985 With amendments as adopted in 2006» makes clear provisions for the enforcement of foreign provisional measures. Article 17H(1) of Section 4. Recognition and enforcement of interim measures of the

Model Law stipulate that: “An interim measure issued by an arbitral tribunal shall be recognized as binding and, unless otherwise provided by the arbitral tribunal, enforced upon application to the competent court, irrespective of the country in which it was issued, subject to the provisions of article 17 I[12].” In order to limit the circumstances in which a court may refuse to enforce an interim measure, article 17(1) of the Model Law stipulates the Grounds for refusing recognition or enforcement of an interim measure, and the same article (2) provides that the court receiving the application to recognize and enforce the interim measure shall not review the substance of the interim measure at the time of making that determination.

(2) International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) Arbitration Rules

The nature, form and effect of the emergency arbitrator's decision are regulated in detail in the «International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) Arbitration Rules». According to Article 29(1)-(3) of the ICC Arbitration Rules, an emergency arbitrator's decision is an urgent interim or conservatory measure, which is made in the form of an order, and the parties undertake to comply with the order made by the emergency arbitrator, i.e. the emergency arbitrator's order is binding on the parties, but not on the arbitral tribunal. The arbitral tribunal may modify, terminate or invalidate the order of the emergency arbitrator. Article 29(4) of the ICC Arbitration Rules further strengthens the binding effect of the emergency arbitrator's order, and the arbitral tribunal may decide on the parties' request regarding the emergency arbitrator's order, including the allocation of the costs

of the proceeding and requests related to compliance or non-compliance with the order. In this way, the emergency arbitrator's order will be further enforced[13].

(3) Hong Kong Arbitration Ordinance

The UNCITRAL Model Law was adopted in the Hong Kong Arbitration Ordinance, which came into force on 1 June 2011, and was given legal effect in Hong Kong through domestic legislation. In 2013, the HKIAC Arbitration Rules provided for the first time for parties to apply for urgent interim or conservatory relief under the emergency arbitrator procedure.

(4) Singapore International Arbitration Act

The UNCITRAL Model Law has also been adopted in the Singapore International Arbitration Act, which provides the arbitral tribunal with the power to issue interim injunctions and any other interim relief measures, and that orders of the arbitral tribunal are enforceable like court orders. The SIAC emergency arbitrator procedure provides that an emergency arbitrator has the power to make a decision or award on such interim measures as he or she considers necessary. A decision or award made under the emergency arbitrator rules is binding on the parties, who agree to arbitrate in accordance with the Rules, and the parties undertake to comply with the interim order or award immediately and without delay.

(5) Conclusion

Singapore and Hong Kong directly provide for the enforceability of emergency arbitrations in their arbitration laws. However, apart from that, there is still a lack of consensus in other countries or regions of the world on the enforceability of emergency arbitrator's decisions. For example, according to Article 28 of the

Arbitration Law of the People's Republic of China, "If a party may make an award unenforceable or difficult to enforce due to the acts of another party or for other reasons, it may apply for the preservation of property. If a party applies for property preservation, the arbitration committee shall submit the party's application to the people's court in accordance with the relevant provisions of the Civil Procedure Law[14]", the arbitral tribunal does not have the right to make decisions on emergency measures, and only judges can make decisions on interlocutory measures such as property preservation. It is doubtful whether the interlocutory measures made by foreign arbitral tribunals are enforceable in China, let alone the enforcement of the decisions made by emergency arbitrators in China. Therefore, when it comes to emergency arbitration decisions that need to be enforced in China, more reliance is placed on the parties' conscious performance.

6. Conclusions and Suggestions

The emergency arbitrator procedure is party-oriented, respects parties' autonomy and meets the parties' needs for urgent interim relief, and thus emergency arbitration is widely applied worldwide to protect the rights of the parties in a timely and comprehensive manner before the constitution of the arbitral tribunal. Except for Hong Kong, Singapore and some countries which have directly provided for the enforceability of emergency arbitration in their arbitration laws, in most countries and regions in the world, arbitral tribunals are not given the power to make relevant conservatory measures or to take interim measures and preliminary orders, and emergency interim measures made by arbitral tribunals still lack a legal basis for

recognition and enforcement. As internationally renowned arbitral institutions, HKIAC and SIAC have set an example for other countries and regions around the world. Countries and regions around the world should take into account the needs of the parties and the development of international arbitration practice and actively introduce emergency arbitrator procedures to further enhance the internationalization of local arbitration institutions. At the same time, taking into

account the emergent needs of parties for urgent interim relief in the global economic environment, countries and regions around the world should take into account the relevant provisions of the UNCITRAL Model Law and amend their arbitration laws to give arbitral institutions the power to make and enforce emergency interim measures, so as to substantially promote the internationalization of local arbitration.

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